

Examining Self-Perceived Competence in Biology Among Junior High School Students: A Descriptive Analysis

Jaybie S. Arzaga

Palawan State University, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan, Philippines

Abstract

Students' self-perceived competence refers to students own perception of their level of competence or ability in a particular area or skill. This study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the self-perceived competencies of Grade 10 students in the field of biology education, specifically focusing on Biology 7, 8, 9, and 10. The study was conducted in a public junior high school in the Philippines. Using a descriptive quantitative research design, data were collected from 76 Grade 10 students through a Rapid Competency Assessment Questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of a comprehensive list of learning competencies in Biology, based on the K to 12 Science Curriculum outlined by the Department of Education. Participants assessed their understanding of each competency using a defined scale ranging from "Excellent" to "Poor." The results of the study revealed the Grade 10 students' perception of their competence in achieving the Grade 7, 8, 9, and 10 Biology competencies. Students believed they performed satisfactorily in the areas of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems. However, they perceived their performance to be fair in the domain of Heredity: Inheritance and Variation. The findings of this study have implications for educational interventions and teacher training programs. The results suggest the need to develop interventions that enhance students' interest and motivation in Biology, as well as improve teaching strategies to address the areas where students perceive their competence to be fair. Additionally, the study supports the Department of Education's efforts to create a favorable learning environment for students by identifying areas for improvement in biology education. Future research may focus on investigating the actual competencies of students in Biology and exploring the factors that contribute to students' perceived competencies. By understanding these factors, educators can better tailor their instructional approaches to enhance students' learning experiences in Biology.

Keywords: *Self-perceived Competence, Biology Education, Junior High School, Descriptive Analysis, Philippines.*

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Introduction

Science education is critically important to both science and the world. It has greatly advanced our understanding of the natural world, leading to the creation of medicines and useful devices. Science education also promotes behaviors that improve lives. The public appreciates the practical benefits of science, even if they are not familiar with how science works or what it has discovered (Alberts, 2008). Science education is undertaken to understand it more clearly and identify ways to improve it. Journals in science education exist to record and disseminate good research in this field. However, science education faces challenges as it takes a central role in both formal and informal education. The future significance of science education journals depends on how these challenges are addressed (Gilbert, 1994). Science education has the opportunity to respond to the rise of misleading information and promote the core values of science and science communication in our society (Marangio & Gunstone, 2020). Science education in schools plays a central role in the training of complex thought in children. It helps in the integral growth of individuals and fosters critical, caring, and creative thinking. Early science education provides opportunities for observation, exploration, research, dialogue, and the development of thinking strategies. It helps individuals become responsible and critical thinkers (Gjipali & Lamaj, 2024). Science education should help students develop sophisticated understandings of what science is, how it is done, and its purposes. It should also help students imagine themselves within scientific activity and consider what counts as science in and out of school (Tucker-Raymond et al., 2012).

Science education in the Philippines has undergone significant reforms to make it more relevant to everyday life and national developmental goals (Tan, 1988). These reforms include integrating local and relevant technologies, value formation, and a learner-based, multidisciplinary approach (Berg, 2010). The Science Teacher Education Project Southern Philippines (STEPS) focused on faculty development to improve science and mathematics education (Dela Fuente, 2019). The project found that practical and applicable pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) can be developed through well-supervised practical thesis studies and intensive team teaching (Feliciano et al., 2013). The qualitative study on students' experiences in specializing in science identified personal interest, nature of science, family influence, and teacher impact as driving factors (Montebon, 2014). The Science Education Institute of the Department of Science and Technology has implemented open learning initiatives to improve access and quality of science and mathematics education. The new K to 12 curriculum in the Philippines has introduced innovations in science education, including the arrangement of competencies, integration of science branches, and learning pedagogies.

Students' self-perceived competence refers to students own perception of their level of competence or ability in a particular area or skill. Students' self-perceived competence in science was examined in several studies. One study conducted on students in Padang City found that students had a high level of self-efficacy in learning science, indicating confidence in their ability to achieve learning goals (Nurhasnah et al., 2022). A study in Greece found that graduating nursing students rated their competence as good and identified factors such as program quality and clinical training as important for competence development (Kiekkas et al., 2019). Additionally, a study in Lithuania found that students' intrinsic motivation for learning science was influenced by their perceived competence and relatedness in responsible research and innovation activities (Pečiuliauskienė, 2019). In the context of science teaching in the

Philippines, students' satisfaction with their science teachers' competence was influenced by their perceived level of competence in areas such as commitment, knowledge of the subject matter, application of teaching strategies, and classroom management (Basas et al., 2020). A study on grade school and high school students revealed that their perceptions of science classes varied across different dimensions, including learner-centered pedagogy, science inquiry activities, positive affect and attitudes, grades as feedback, and support for self-learning and effort (Bernardo et al., 2008). Self-perceived competence is an integral aspect of self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's belief in their ability to perform specific tasks or achieve desired outcomes. Assessing self-perceived competence offers several benefits, as it provides insights into a student's motivation to maintain and improve their skills. Extensive research has explored the influence of self-efficacy on student learning and the attainment of academic goals. Students with high levels of self-efficacy exhibit confidence in their capacity to understand lessons, tackle educational obstacles, and successfully complete tasks.

There are many studies conducted with regards to students' perceived competence. However, there are only a few research in the literature that have looked at the self-perceived competence of the students in Biology. In the K-12 curriculum, Biology or Life Science is one of the domains. In Grade 7, it is taught in the second quarter, in Grade 8 in fourth quarter, in Grade 9 in first quarter, and in Grade 10 in third quarter. Biology is one of the branches of science (Earla, 2015). It is the study of living organisms, their growth, function, structure, and evolution (Delalande et al, 2020). The word "biology" originated from the Greek words "logia" meaning study of and "bios" meaning life (Kanazawa, 2004). Biology encompasses various sub-disciplines such as anatomy and physiology, biochemistry, genetics, microbiology, botany, and zoology. It is a fundamental science that is interconnected with the daily life of all living creatures, increasing its significance over time. The study of biology attracts students of all abilities and particularly appeals to girls. While biology is essential in understanding living organisms and their behavior, it is also important to recognize that social sciences, which study human behavior and social systems, can be considered branches of biology as well.

This research study offers a comprehensive understanding of the present state of students' self-perceived competence in the field of biology education, encompassing the full implementation of the curriculum. Its objective is to provide valuable insights for teachers and educators on how to enhance academic performance and foster lifelong learning. Recognizing the significance of biology competence, the study aims to examine the self-perceived competence levels of Grade 10 students in a public junior high school in the Philippines, specifically focusing on Biology 7, 8, 9, and 10.

Objectives

This study aimed to assess the self-perceived competence of students enrolled at Bahile National High School during the school year 2017-2018, specifically focusing on their understanding of Life Science or Biology. The study had the following specific objectives: (1) to determine the self-perceived competence of Grade 7 students in the areas of parts and function (animals and plants), heredity (inheritance and variation), and ecosystems; (2) to determine the self-perceived competence of Grade 8 students in the areas of parts and function (animals and plants), heredity (inheritance and variation), biodiversity and evolution, and ecosystems; (3) to determine the self-

perceived competence of Grade 9 students in the areas of parts and function (animals and plants), heredity (inheritance and variation), biodiversity and evolution, and ecosystems; and (4) to determine the self-perceived competence of Grade 10 students in the areas of parts and function (animals and plants), heredity (inheritance and variation), biodiversity and evolution, and ecosystems.

Methodology

The research design employed in this study was descriptive quantitative, which facilitated the researchers in gaining insights and providing a description of the self-perceived competencies of the learners. It involved a total of 76 junior high school students from a public secondary school within one school division in the Department of Education (DepEd) MIMAROPA, Philippines, during the school year 2017-2018. These participants were grade 10 students at the time of the study and completed a rapid competency assessment questionnaire to evaluate their self-perceived competencies.

Prior to conducting the study, the researcher obtained permission from the School Principal and discussed the rationale and proposed schedules of the research. The principal approved the study, and the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the students. The section advisers of the participating students were also informed about the study. The data collection process involved the use of a researcher-made Rapid Competency Assessment Questionnaire, which encompassed a comprehensive list of learning competencies in Biology as outlined in the K to 12 Science Curriculum by the Department of Education (2016). The questionnaire was validated by five experts in the field of Biology and Biology education from universities and other high schools in the region. Students assessed their understanding of each competency based on their perception and selected appropriate choices from the provided options. The interpretation of the scores was based on a defined scale, ranging from "Excellent" to "Poor," with corresponding percentage mastery levels for each competency:

Table 1. Rapid Competency Assessment Score, Description, and Interpretation

Score	Description	Interpretation
4.51–5.0	Excellent	Students believed to have 91–100% mastery of the learning competency.
3.51–4.50	Very Satisfactory	Students believed to have 71–90% mastery of the learning competency.
2.51–3.50	Satisfactory	Students believed to have 41–70% mastery of the learning competency.
1.51–2.50	Fair	Students believed to have 21–40% mastery of the learning competency.
1.00 - 1.50	Poor	Students believed to have 0–20% mastery of the learning competency.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS, and descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were utilized to describe the self-perceived competencies of the junior high school students.

Results and Discussion

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 illustrate the self-perceived competency of students in Grade 7 Biology. The overall self-perceived competency was assessed as satisfactory, with a mean (M) score of 2.95 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.73. The specific categories of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Heredity: Inheritance and Variation, and Ecosystems were also considered satisfactory. It is worth noting that there were no competencies related to Biodiversity and Evolution in Grade 7 Biology. Based on the data, students in Grade 7 Biology perceived their mastery of the learning competencies in all domains to be within the 41–70 percent range.

Table 2. Students Self-Perceived Competence in Grade 7 Biology

GRADE 7				
Biology Area	n	SD	M	Description
Parts and Function: Animals and Plants	76	0.69	3.00	Satisfactory
Heredity: Inheritance and Variation	76	0.73	3.16	Satisfactory
Ecosystems	76	0.76	2.68	Satisfactory
TOTAL	76	0.73	2.95	Satisfactory

Note: 4.51–5.0 = Excellent; 3.51–4.50 = Very Satisfactory; 2.51–3.50 = Satisfactory; 1.51–2.50 = Fair, 1.0–1.50 = Poor.

Table 3. Students Self-Perceived Competence in Grade 8 Biology

GRADE 8				
Biology Area	n	SD	M	Description
Parts and Function: Animal and Plants	76	.68	2.83	Satisfactory
Heredity: Inheritance and Variation	76	.79	2.54	Satisfactory
Biodiversity and Evolution	76	.66	2.72	Satisfactory
Ecosystems	76	.74	2.85	Satisfactory
TOTAL	76	.72	2.76	Satisfactory

Note: 4.51–5.0 = Excellent; 3.51–4.50 = Very Satisfactory; 2.51–3.50 = Satisfactory; 1.51–2.50 = Fair, 1.0–1.50 = Poor.

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for the self-perceived competency of students in Grade 8 Biology. The overall self-perceived competency was assessed as satisfactory, with a mean (M) score of 2.76 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.72. Additionally, the specific domains of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Heredity: Inheritance and Variation, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems were all considered satisfactory. According to the data, students in Grade 8 Biology perceived their mastery of the learning competencies in all areas to be within the 41–70 percent range.

The self-perceived competency of students in Grade 9 Biology is presented in Table 4, indicating the descriptive statistics. The overall self-perceived competency was

determined to be satisfactory, with a mean (M) score of 2.77 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.94. Specifically, the domains of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems were rated as satisfactory. According to the data, students in Grade 9 Biology perceived their mastery of the learning competencies in these domains to be within the 41–70 percent range. However, in the domain of Heredity: Inheritance and Variation, students believed their mastery level to be fair, with 21–40 percent proficiency in the learning abilities related to this area.

Table 4. Students Self-Perceived Competence in Grade 9 Biology

GRADE 9				
Biology Area	n	SD	M	Description
Parts and Function: Animal and Plants	76	.98	2.93	Satisfactory
Heredity: Inheritance and Variation	76	.96	2.43	Fair
Biodiversity and Evolution	76	.88	2.83	Satisfactory
Ecosystems	76	.92	2.88	Satisfactory
TOTAL	76	.94	2.77	Satisfactory

Note: 4.51–5.0 = Excellent; 3.51–4.50 = Very Satisfactory; 2.51–3.50 = Satisfactory; 1.51–2.50 = Fair, 1.0–1.50 = Poor.

Table 5. Students Self-Perceived Competence in Grade 10 Biology

GRADE 7				
Biology Area	n	SD	M	Description
Parts and Function: Animal and Plants	76	.92	2.83	Satisfactory
Heredity: Inheritance and Variation	76	.87	2.38	Fair
Biodiversity and Evolution	76	.97	2.72	Satisfactory
Ecosystems	76	.79	2.83	Satisfactory
TOTAL	76	.89	2.69	Satisfactory

Note: 4.51–5.0 = Excellent; 3.51–4.50 = Very Satisfactory; 2.51–3.50 = Satisfactory; 1.51–2.50 = Fair, 1.0–1.50 = Poor.

Table 5 displays the descriptive statistics for the self-perceived competency of students in Grade 10 Biology. The overall self-perceived competence level was assessed as satisfactory, with a mean (M) score of 2.69 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.89. The specific domains of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems were all rated as satisfactory. Based on the data, students in Grade 10 Biology perceived their mastery of the learning competencies in these areas to be within the 41–70 percent range. However, in the domain of Heredity: Inheritance and Variation, students considered their mastery to be fair, with 21–40 percent proficiency in the learning competencies related to this domain.

The results indicating “satisfactory” self-perceived competency in Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9, and Grade 10 Biology suggest that students have a lower level of confidence in their mastery of the learning competencies in Biology. It is important to note that

the term "satisfactory" used here refers to the self-perceived competency scores and does not necessarily reflect the actual competence of the students. The findings highlight areas of concern and potential challenges in the students' understanding of Biology concepts. Specifically, the domain of Heredity: Inheritance and Variation consistently received "fair" ratings, indicating that students perceive their mastery in this area to be particularly weak. This could suggest a need for focused attention and instructional support to improve students' understanding and confidence in this domain.

The satisfactory ratings for the domains of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems indicate that students generally perceive their competency in these areas to be at an acceptable level. However, it is worth noting that the self-perceived competency scores still fall within the 41–70 percent range, suggesting room for improvement and further development of students' understanding in these domains as well. The implications of these results point towards the need for targeted interventions and instructional strategies to address the identified areas of low self-perceived competency. Educators and curriculum developers can use these findings to inform their teaching practices, focusing on reinforcing concepts related to heredity and variation, and providing additional support to enhance students' understanding and confidence in these areas. It is crucial to consider that self-perceived competency may not always align with actual mastery of the subject matter. Therefore, it is recommended to supplement these self-perceived assessments with objective measures, such as exams or assessments, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of students' actual competencies in Biology.

CONCLUSION

The following statements are based on the results of the study:

1. The self-perceived competency of Grade 10 students indicates that they believe they performed satisfactorily in achieving the Grade 7 Biology competencies related to Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Heredity: Inheritance and Variation, and Ecosystems.
2. The self-perceived competency of Grade 10 students suggests that they believe they performed satisfactorily in achieving the Grade 8 Biology competencies across all domains, including Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Heredity: Inheritance and Variation, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems.
3. According to the self-perceived competency ratings of Grade 10 students, they believe they performed satisfactorily in achieving the Grade 9 Biology competencies in the domains of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems. However, they perceive their performance to be fair in the domain of Heredity: Inheritance and Variation.
4. The self-perceived competency ratings of Grade 10 students indicate that they believe they performed satisfactorily in achieving the Grade 10 Biology competencies in the domains of Parts and Function: Animals and Plants, Biodiversity and Evolution, and Ecosystems. However, they perceive their performance to be fair in the domain of Heredity: Inheritance and Variation.

Recommendations

1. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended to develop and implement educational interventions that can enhance students' interest and motivation in Biology. These interventions can help improve students' actual performance and, subsequently, their perception of their attainment of learning competencies in the subject.
2. The study highlights the importance of teacher training programs that focus on both content knowledge and pedagogical expertise. By improving the teaching-learning process, these programs can contribute to enhancing students' understanding and competence in Biology. It is suggested that a comprehensive reform program for teachers be considered to address these needs.
3. The results of this study align with the Department of Education's goal of creating a favorable learning environment for students. The findings emphasize the need to provide support and resources to improve students' competencies in Biology, ensuring that the learning environment facilitates their growth and understanding in the subject.
4. Future research can explore the actual competencies of students in Biology and examine the relationship between perceived and actual competencies. Additionally, investigating the factors that contribute to students' perceived competencies in Biology would provide valuable insights for further improvement in teaching and learning approaches.

References

- Alberts, B. (2008). Considering science education. *Science*, 319(5870), 1589-1589. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1157518>
- Basas, A. B., Cornillez, E. E., Balagasay, M. A., & Cinco, L. (2020). Science teachers teaching competence and students' satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management*, 1(1), 1-9.
- Bernardo, A. B., Limjap, A. A., Prudente, M. S., & Roleda, L. S. (2008). Students' perceptions of science classes in the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 9(3), 285-295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03026717>
- Dela Fuente, J. A. (2019). Driving forces of students' choice in specializing science: A science education context in the Philippines perspective. *The Normal Lights*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.56278/tnl.v13i2.1393>
- Delalande, B., Tamagawa, H., & Matveev, V. (2020). From nernst to Bernstein and beyond. *OALib*, 07(12), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1107047>
- Earla, P. (2015). Biology and its significance. *Research & Reviews: Journal of Biology*.
- Feliciano, J., Mandapat, L. C., & Khan, C. (2013). Harnessing the use of open learning exchange to support basic education in science and mathematics in the Philippines. *US-China Education Review*, 03(06), 407-416.
- Gilbert, J. K. (1994). On the significance of journals in science education: The case of IJSE. *International Journal of Science Education*, 16(4), 375-384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950069940160401>

- Gjipali, A., & Lamaj, I. (2014). The importance of scientific education in the primary school. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5901/jesr.2014.v4n4p357>
- K to 12 Curriculum Guide SCIENCE*. (2016). Department of Education. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Science-CG_with-tagged-sci-equipment_revised.pdf
- Kanazawa, S. (2004). Social sciences are branches of biology. *Socio-Economic Review*, 2(3), 371-390. <https://doi.org/10.1093/soceco/2.3.371>
- Kiekkas, P., Michalopoulos, E., Igoumenidis, M., Michalopoulos, A., & Stefanopoulos, N. (2019). Factors associated with self-reported competence of graduating nursing students. *Collegian*, 26(2), 267-272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colegn.2018.08.004>
- Marangio, K., & Gunstone, R. (2020). Science as “Just opinion” – The significance for science education of emerging social media. *Values in Science Education*, 69-89. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-42172-4_5
- Montebon, D. R. (2014). K12 science program in the Philippines: Student perception on its implementation. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(12).
- Nurhasnah, N., Lufri, L., Andromed, A., & Mufit, F. (2022). Analysis of students' self efficacy in science learning. *Unnes Science Education Journal*, 11(2), 109-114. <https://doi.org/10.15294/usej.v11i2.58458>
- Pečiuliauskienė, P. (2019). School students' intrinsic motivation for learning science in RRI activity: The influence of perceived competence and relatedness. *Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 11(3), 180-200. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/144>
- Tan, M. C. (1988). Towards relevance in science education: Philippine context. *International Journal of Science Education*, 10(4), 431-440. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950069880100410>
- Tucker-Raymond, E., Varelas, M., Pappas, C. C., & Keblawe-Shamah, N. (2012). Young children's multimodal identity stories about being scientists. *Identity Construction and Science Education Research*, 79-95. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6209-043-9_6
- Van den Berg, E. (2015). Generating pedagogical content knowledge in teacher education students. *Physics Education*, 50(5), 573-579. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-9120/50/5/573>

